

Level of Occupational Stress and Coping Resources of Selected Employees in a Higher Education Institution

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Abstract

This paper sought to determine the occupational stress and coping resources of workers of a selected Higher Education Institution in Bacoor City, Cavite, in the hope that these can become the bases for an appropriate Human Resource Training Program for the employees. To address this main problem, this study utilized the descriptive design with 40 respondents. The results show that among the occupational stress, physical environment ($x=58.75$, $SD=9.09$) gives the employees so much stress; this is followed by role insufficiency ($x=56.92$, $SD=9.34$), role boundary ($x=48.78$, $SD=10.02$), and last is role ambiguity ($x=44.62$, $SD=5.93$). Among all coping resources, it is self-care which helps workers to deal with occupational stress. Moreover, women, more than men, consider physical environment to be a source of occupational stress. The researcher recommends conducting a survey that gears toward determining the occupational stress of workers, crafting a program that aims at improving the coping resources of workers, and conducting a qualitative study to determine how employees can improve or enhance their coping resources and eventually also enhance their performance with regards to their occupational stress.

Keywords: Occupational stress. Coping resources. Human training resource program. Descriptive research.

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Introduction

Life in the 21st century necessitates some capabilities to overcome life threatening stress. Further, one needs strength to surpass challenges and trials and equally important, sustenance to pursue a purpose-driven life. In many occasions, stress is experienced, may it be beneficial or harmful. Beneficial stress can positively drive a people to really work more until they achieve utmost fulfillment and success. However, harmful stress may cause feelings of despondency to such an extent that it may drive people to despair and hopelessness. Thus, coping with it necessitates looking for ways and means that help a person preserve one's life and sanity.

Apparently, stress affects physical and health well-being as well. It also leads to emotional disturbances and typical symptoms such as "mood swings and erratic behavior which can start a vicious circle of decreasing confidence, leading to more serious emotional problems." Individuals suffering from any level of stress may lose their ability to make sound decisions. This may affect their health, families as well as their careers which would need a sense of stability and wellness.

Moreover, establishing basic needs at work would necessarily entail certain struggles to learn how to reduce stress which affects almost all of the people at some time in their lives. Such struggles towards reaching professional goals will allow individuals achieve them without damaging their lives if they overcome stress. Changes like rapid increase in urbanization, population growth, developing gender sensitivity roles and the breakthroughs in science and technology would cause stress. Such changes, vital in a society's endeavors would need employees' greater and more persistent efforts with arduousness.

The many changes in society will certainly need employees' utmost struggle to respond to pressure and stress. Competitions among employees and corporations have become greater and wider to an extent that they need to pursue certain strategies that put them under stress. In the quest for improvements among employees, motivations in several forms are afforded to employees. To develop the full potential of employees, organizations are rapidly moving away from "command and control" and towards "advise and consent" as ways of motivating people. This change of attitude began when employees recognized that rewarding good work is more effective than threatening punitive measures for bad work. In the context of work, work-related stress is an issue that strongly impacts every employee, organization, and communities (Harzer and Ruch, 2015, as cited in Hodapp et. al, 2005; Vagg & Spielberger, 1998).

High performing organizations promote employee productivity with the end in view of attaining organizational health and stability. Recent research shows a direct correlation between job-related stress and organizational productivity. Organizations that are able to manage or address job-related stress help individual, career and organizational development. Failure to address this problem leads to organizational loss, customers' dissatisfaction, and decrease in profit.

This research intends to look into the various occupational stress and different coping resources of workers. The degrees of coping resources with work-related conflict situation of the respondents are very much related to the identification of the different job-related stress. Further, this sought to answer the following questions: (1) What is the profile of the selected respondents in terms of? a) sex; b) job assignment; and c) length of service; (2) What is their Occupational Stress associated with? a) role insufficiency; b) role ambiguity; c) role boundary; d) responsibility; and e) physical environment; (3) What is the rating of the coping resources in terms of? a) recreation; b) self-care; c) social support; and d) rational and cognitive coping.

Methodology

This study used the descriptive design. According to Polit and Beck (2010), descriptive research describes systematically a situation or area of interest factually and accurately. It is a method of description of phenomena based on the collection of data and statistical analysis of numerical values.

This study was conducted in St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor City, Cavite. The participants of this study are employees who have been connected with this institution for the last four years (from 2013 to 2017). They come from different departments of the school, from the administration, faculty to the staff. Using universal sampling, the study involved all the employees of the academic institution, who met the following inclusion criteria: have been working with SDCA for the last four years, willing to participate in the study, and who have signed the informed consent.

This study utilized a 140-item questionnaire which is based on Occupational Stress Inventory-Revised" (OSI-R) (Psychological Assessment Resources, Inc.) scale which measures domains of occupational adjustment that include not only occupational stress, but also stress associated with one's inability to cope effectively with stressors in the workplace and other settings, as well as the coping resources available to the individual to combat the effects of stressors and to alleviate strain.

Occupational stress is measured by a set of six scales that comprise the **Occupational Roles Questionnaire (ORQ)**. The ORQ scales measure the following stress-inducing work roles:

Role Overload (RO). High-scoring individuals may characterize their workload as increasing, excessive, and lacking in resources. They can claim that they are under-trained or incompetent for the job, that they need additional assistance, and/or that they are working under strict deadlines.

Role Insufficiency (RI). High scorers can complain about a disparity between their abilities and the job they are doing. They can also say that their career is steadily declining and has no potential. It is indeed possible that the needs for validation and achievement are not being fulfilled and that they can complain about boredom and/or underuse.

Role Ambiguity (RA). High-scoring individuals will have a vague understanding about what they are supposed to do, how they can invest their time, and how they will be judged. They seem to not know where to start on new tasks and are dealing with conflicting demands from their bosses. They can even say they have no idea what they can do to "get ahead."

Role Boundary (RB). High-scoring employees can feel frustrated between competing supervisory demands and factions. They can express dissatisfaction with their work or a lack of ownership in a company. They can also say that authority lines are overlapping, and that more than one person is asking them what to do.

Responsibility (R). High scorers may claim a lot of responsibility for their subordinates' activities and job success. They are concerned that others will fail to deliver. They are often called upon to provide leadership and often have to deal with the concerns of others. They might still have strained relationships at work or be under pressure from dealing with irate or challenging coworkers or the general public.

Physical Environment (PE). High-scoring individuals may have been subject to excessive noise, moisture, toxic chemicals, or foul odors, among others. They can even complain about a sporadic work schedule or a sense of personal isolation.

Coping resources are measured by four scales that comprise the **Personal Resources Questionnaire (PRQ)**:

Recreation (RE). High scorers can say that they make the most of the recreational/leisure time available to them by participating in a variety of relaxing and fulfilling activities. They can even mention what they enjoy doing in their spare time.

Self-Care (SC). High scorers can say they exercise regularly, sleep eight hours a day, eat healthily, use relaxing strategies, and avoid harmful substances (e.g., alcohol, drugs, tobacco, coffee).

Social Support (SS). High scorers can feel as though they have at least one person they can rely on, someone who trusts and/or loves them. They can mention having sympathetic people with whom to discuss job issues, as well as having assistance with essential tasks and/or household chores. They can also express feelings of attachment to another person.

Rational/Cognitive Coping (RC). High scorers may claim to have a comprehensive approach to problem solving, consider the implications of their decisions, and be able to recognize key elements of problems they face. They can use it to set and pursue goals, as well as to have strategies for avoiding distractions. They may even report they will reexamine and understand their job routine.

The researcher assured the participants of utmost confidentiality of the results of their psychological test and survey sheets. The researcher also understood that people's consciousness may also affect their honesty and effectiveness in answering the survey, and so, the researcher gave the participants the option of being anonymous. There were no incentives, or any remuneration offered for the participants of this research.

The researcher used the frequency and percentage for the demographic profile in which tallying of number of occurrences done and percentage of the frequency versus the overall frequency was determined. Moreover, weighted mean was used to determine the level of occupational stress and coping strategies of selected employees.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 Summary of demographic profile (n=40)

Demographic Profile	Variables	n	%
Sex	Male	23	57.5
	Female	17	42.5
Job Assignment	Academic Services	24	60
	Administrative Services	16	40
Length of Service	4-7 years	11	27.5
	8-11 years	23	57.5
	12-15 years	6	15

Table 1 reflects the demographic profile of the 40 participants of this study showing that majority of them are males (57.5%). Of the 40 participants, 60% belong to the academic services and 40% to the administrative services. Also, 57.5% of them have worked in the institution for 8-11 years. This is closely followed by those who have worked for 4-7 years (27.5%), while only 15% have stayed with the institution for 12-15 years.

Research has indicated that gender has an impact on occupational stress of an employee (Dcunha, 2017, as cited in Prasad, et al., 2016) and that male and female differ in their stress and coping process (Watson et al., 2011, as cited in Shafaghat et al., 2018) which may be due to the difference in psychosocial factors. Females have significantly higher scores on sources of stress (Kim, et al, 2016, as cited in Lim & Teo, 1996).

Other studies also revealed that occupational stress is due to job assignment (Shafaghat et al., 2018) where middle-level employees are less vulnerable to occupational stress than operational level employees (Haque et al., 2018).

Research studies also revealed that there is a significant existence of a negative relationship between length of service and role stress (Prasad & Vaidya, 2018, as cited in Elahi & Apoorva, 2012), but negative result was found in a study of physicians where the higher the length of service the higher the level of stress (Stanetic & Tesanovic, 2018).

Table 2 Summary of means, standard deviations, and ranks of occupational stress (n=40)

Aspects of Occupational Stress	Mean	SD	Rank
Physical Environment	58.75	9.09	1
Role Insufficiency	56.92	9.34	2
Responsibility	51.80	10.63	3
Role Boundary	48.78	10.02	4
Role Ambiguity	44.62	5.93	5
Overall Level of Occupational Stress	50.05	12.34	

When it comes to occupational stress that the participants experienced in the institution, it can be gleaned from Table 2 that the overall occupational stress has a mean of 50.05. Physical environment contributes the most in the occupational stress the participants experience (x=58.75, SD=9.09).

Physical environment is closely followed by role insufficiency (x=56.92, SD=9.34). The least occupational stress comes from role ambiguity (x=44.62, SD=5.93). Michie (2002) posits that the workplace is an important source of both demands and pressures causing stress, and structural and social resources to counteract stress.

Situations that are likely to cause stress are those that are unpredictable or uncontrollable, uncertain, ambiguous or unfamiliar, or involving conflict, loss of performance expectations. It may also be caused by time limited events, such as the pressures of examinations or work deadlines, or by ongoing situations, such as family demands, job insecurity, or long commuting journeys. It is natural that the physical environment came in a first because of the heavy traffic Bacoor City has been experiencing for almost five years. Compounding this problem is the construction of new buildings that have been ongoing for almost five years. The accreditations that the institution has been into every year starting five to six years ago, has contributed to the stressful physical environment of the institution. Although, this is not true with other institutions as Michie and Williams (2003) asserted that there are key factors that are associated with psychological ill health and associated absenteeism, that are closely related to occupational stress. They are long hours work, working overload, and pressure; the effects of these on personal lives; lack of control over work and lack of participation in decision making; poor social support; and unclear management and work role and poor management style.

In studying a new model of seven team roles, most roles contributed to job satisfaction and work calling, and only a few relationships were found for ideal roles (Gander et al., 2018). Research studies revealed that role ambiguity has positive and significant relationship on stress (Syahril, 2011) and on full mediation on emotional exhaustion (Celik, 2013) that lead to burnout.

In a study by Lease (1999), there were no significant differences on measures of stress or strain between male and female faculty or between new and more experienced faculty members. She pointed out that role overload and avoidant coping were significant predictors of strain measures with hardiness and responsibility for home-centered tasks. In a study of 832 employees across 96 departments, strengths use support reduced absenteeism among workers with a high workload and high emotional demands (van Woerkom et al., 2016).

According to Ashforth and Humphrey (1993), some effects of emotional labor are moderated by one's social and personal identities and that emotional labor stimulates occupational stress for the person to identify with the service role. Same result was found on the role stress in nurses where one of the innovative ways of supporting them is enhancing social and peer support (Chang et al., 2005). Stress in the work environment typically focuses on psychosocial factors that affect job performance, strain and employee health, and does not address the growing body of work on the environmental psychology of workspace (Vischer, 2007). In some research, teachers attribute responsibility for their occupational stress to entities increasingly 'distant' from themselves (McCormick & Solman, 1992).

Table 3 Summary of means, standard deviations, and ranks of coping resources (n=40)

Aspects of Occupational Stress	Mean	SD	Rank
Physical Environment	58.75	9.09	1
Role Insufficiency	56.92	9.34	2
Responsibility	51.80	10.63	3
Role Boundary	48.78	10.02	4
Overall Level of Occupational Stress	50.05	12.34	

Meanwhile, coping resources has an overall of 56.95. Of this, the highest coping resource happens to be in self-care ($x=59.20$, $SD=12.31$), while the least coping resource is social support ($x=54.05$, $SD=7.74$). It is interesting to note that literature says that the prevention and management of workplace stress requires organizational level interventions, because it is an organization that creates the stress. However, in this study, it shows that workers resort to self-care more than anything else. Organizational interventions can be of many types, ranging from structural (for example, staffing levels, work schedules, and physical environment) to psychology (Michie, 2002).

According to the study on the relationship between the coping resources (as measured by the Coping Resources Inventory) and personality types (as measured by the Myers-Briggs Type Indicator) personality types differ in terms of the level of their coping resources and that the participants' personality types have a significant influence on the level of their coping resources (for example, social support, control over work, participation) (Coetzee et al., 2009).

In the study among clinical psychologists, social workers, nurses, physicians, supervisors, office workers, teachers, and economists, there were connections found among the 24 character strengths and a range of work-related outcomes and that the highest strengths differed based on the facet of job satisfaction, the age of the participants, and the particular occupation (Heintz & Ruch, 2020).

Some studies examine the impact of strengths for employee functioning and discuss antecedents for strengths use, such as organizational support, personal initiative, autonomy, and development opportunities (van Woerkom et al., 2015, as cited in Bakker & van Woerkom, 2018) while it was supervisor support, not colleague support, of employee strengths use that was predictive of increased strengths used the next day (Lavy et al., 2016).

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study sought to determine the level of occupational stress and coping resources of workers of a selected higher education institution in Bacoor City, Cavite. Occupational stress and coping strategies of the employees in the subject institution do not differ with each other and this is regardless of sex, job assignment and length of service. Meanwhile, any difference in occupational stress may be due to psychosocial factors between males and females and adopting differently in specific process models when encountering a stressful situation at work (Watson et al., 2011). Physical environment is the highest overall occupational stress experienced by the participants in the institution, while self-care is the highest overall coping resource.

In the light of all the foregoing, the following recommendations are made: (1) Conduct a survey that gears toward determining the occupational stress of workers; (2) Craft a program that aims at improving the coping resources of workers; and (3) Conduct a qualitative study to determine how employees can improve or enhance their coping resources and eventually also enhance their performance with regards to their occupational stress.

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